

Persistent Organic Pollutants and their Harmful Effects

Paper Id : 18899 Submission Date : 15/05/2024 Acceptance Date : 21/05/2024 Publication Date : 25/05/2024

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.12577787

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Abstract

Persistent organic pollutants are those pollutants which stay in environment and exert deleterious effects slowly. Persistent organic pollutants include insecticides, pesticides, herbicides, dioxins and furans.

Their effects are serious and travel from the source to distant objects through our natural food chain. Almost every vertebrate is forced to face these pollutants. People are exposed to these pollutants either by dermal absorption, inhalation or ingestion.

Initially several POPs have recognized causing hazardous effects in to three categories as pesticides, industrial chemicals and by products. Pesticides are very harmful as they exert serious impact in food chain as side effects after performing their function. Some harmful insecticides which functions as POPs are aldrin, chlordane, DDT(di chloro di phenyle tri chloro ethane),dieldrin, endrin, heptachlor, hexachlorobenzene, mirex, toxaphene, etc.

Similarly studies have shown that the chemical pesticides linger in the atmosphere, soil and water resources long after the job is over. Both insecticides and pesticides contain chemicals that are detrimental to humans when misapplied, spilled or disposed of improperly. It can cause acute allergic reactions within 24 hours of exposures.

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Another group of organic pollutants which are produced as by products of industrial processes or uncontrolled burning of domestic wastes in incinerators are dioxins and furans.

Keywords POPS, Dioxins, Incinerators, Insecticides, Pesticides.

Introduction

Persistent organic Pollutants are organic compounds that are resistant to environmental degradation through chemical, biological and photolytic processes. Due to their persistent nature they bio accumulate with potential adverse impact on human health.

The effect of POPs on human and environmental health was discussed, with intention to eliminate or merely restrict their production, by the international community at the Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants in 2001. Since then we are continuously adding POPs to the environment unknowingly as pesticides, solvents, pharmaceuticals and industrial chemicals. Although some POPs arise naturally, for example volcanoes and various biosynthetic pathways most are manmade via total synthesis.

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DDT being persistent once introduced in the environment, it keeps circulating for many years. Its level keeps on increasing from plankton to clams to fish which feed on clams from .04ppm to 75.5ppm. According to findings of the WHO some 7.5 lakhs people are poisoned by pesticides every year, resulting in some 14000 deaths. Developing countries account for only 30% of the pesticides consumption, but share more than 60% of the casualties.

Objective of study The objective of this paper is to study about the persistent organic pollutants and their harmful effects.

Review of Literature Many books, research papers from online and offline sources has been reviewed for this paper which has been discussed through out the paper.

Main Text

Unfortunately when pesticides are applied to a surface they travel outside their area of use by air soil or water. The Agricultural MU Guide, Pesticides and the Environment, explains that pesticides to be effective, they must move within soil, too much movement can transfer a pesticide away from the target pest. This can lead to reduce pest control, contamination of surface water and ground water and harmful effect on non target species including humans. Both insecticides and pesticides contain chemicals are detrimental to humans when misapplied, spilled or disposed of improperly. It can cause acute allergic reactions within 24 hours of exposures.

Allergic reactions may include difficult breathing, asthma attack, skin and nose irritation, and watering of the eyes. Chronic poisoning may cause physical and neurological effects such as nervousness, slow movement, spasm and decline in good health. Chronic poisoning may be difficult to treat especially if the source of the poisoning is not known. Insecticides run off can also negatively impact surrounding wild life by killing or poisoning food supplies such as insects or plants. Similarly pesticides benefit the crop but they may impose hazardous impact on the environment. Excessive use may lead to destruction of biodiversity. Acute health effects may include stinging eye rashes, blisters, blindness, nausea, dizziness, diarrhoea, various types of carcinoma and ultimately death.

Another group of POPS which we are bound to face today are dioxins and furans. Dioxin contamination has become an imposing problem in many developing countries particularly due to uncontrolled burning, and dismantling of electronic products such as computers. They affect a number of organs as well as organism. Both insecticides and pesticides contain chemicals are detrimental to humans when misapplied, spilled or disposed of improperly. It can cause acute allergic reactions within 24 hours of exposures.

The main characteristic of dioxins is that they are insoluble in water but have a high affinity for lipids. In addition, they tend to associate with organic matters such as ash soil and plant leaves. They are hidden in fat tissues of animals and absorbed and therefore accumulate in the food chain and travel from one trophic level to another. Half life in the human body is estimated to be 7 to 11years. During this long period they cause various health disorders in human beings. Some serious harmful effects are skin lesions, reproductive disorders, endocrine malfunction and skin cancers. They function as slow poison in nature because once they enter in to food chain they exert their harmful effect in long course. According to New York Times the dioxin in mother's milk came largely from food. This study was conducted on samples of breast milk from 50 women. (Dec 18, 1987). Dioxins and furans are released in to the environment unintentionally as by product of industrial process. There are different types of dioxins and Furans present in the environment some of them are very poisonous. Most toxic one is 2,3,7,8 *tetrachloro p-dibenzo* dioxin. Some polychlorinated biphenyls [PCBs] with some toxic properties are also included in this category. There are 75 *chlorinated dibenzodioxins* 7 have TCDD like toxicity .There are 135 *chlorinated dibenzofurans* 10 have TCDD like toxicity. There are 209 chlorinated biphenyl [PCBs] 13 have TCDD like toxicity. There are also *brominated dibenzodioxins, dibenzofurans* and biphenyls that have TCDD like toxicity.

Dioxins are unwanted by products of a wide range of manufacturing processes like smelting, chlorine bleaching of paper pulp and manufacturing of some herbicides and pesticides .When it comes to the dioxin release in to the environment uncontrolled waste incinerators [solid wastes and hospital wastes] are often immediate sources due to incomplete burning. Although dioxins were used as an ingredients in several herbicides in

the united states in the 1960 and 1970s but 2,3,7,8-TCDD is most infamous for its toxic activity. Dioxins were used as an ingredients in several herbicides in the united states in the 1960 and 1970s but 2,3,7,8-TCDD is most infamous for its toxic activity.

Deposition from atmospheric dioxin makes soil inappropriate for plant growth. Dioxins are unwanted by products of a wide range of manufacturing processes like smelting, chlorine bleaching of paper pulp and manufacturing of some herbicides and pesticides .When it comes to the dioxin release in to the environment uncontrolled waste incinerators [solid wastes and hospital wastes]are often immediate sources due to incomplete burning.

In 2008, Ireland recalled many tons of pork meat and pork products when about 200 time than safe limit of dioxins was detected in samples of pork. In 1999 high level of dioxins were found in poultry and eggs from Belgium. The reason was found to be illegally disposed PCB based waste industrial oil. Strict regulatory controls on major industrial sources of dioxins have reduced emissions in to the air by 90%, compared to levels in 1987.

Dioxin forms a layer on surface of water bodies and contaminated soil washed off during rainy season becomes a major source. Deposition from atmospheric dioxin makes soil inappropriate for plant growth. Other reasons include contaminated sewage sludge forming land and contaminated milk forming sludge in land.

A major source of Dioxin in India is Polyvinyl chloride (PVC) both during its production and disposal. Burning of unsegregated waste containing PVC is a common practise in India. Plastic percentage is increasing in our waste. The central pollution control board (CPCB) estimated that at present Indian Plastic industry produces more than 70,000 tonnes of PVC a month. The most dangerous emissions can be caused by burning plastic containing PVC.

Pollutants released from burning plastics are transported through the air short or long distances and or deposited on to land or bodies of water. Our government is going to ban single use plastic bags, cups, and plates to fight against global warming and pollution. The condition is going to be very critical in developing country like India where people are unaware of situation. At present our India is passing through worst phase of pollution nearly half of our country is bound to breathe poisonous air. Air quality index has crossed around 500. Out of five most polluted cities two belongs to UP. A kind of environmental emergency is declared and government is going to take serious action.

Dioxins in Food and their Regulation

Almost all humans are regularly exposed to low level of dioxin through inhalation, ingestion or skin contact, ingestion of food containing dioxins accounts for 90% exposure without knowing. Dioxins and Furans persist for a long period and have a tendency to bioaccumulate which means they build up in Predators at the top of the food web. Most important thing about dioxins is that bioaccumulation of these pollutants occurs indirectly through contaminated food and water rather than breathing the contaminated air directly.

Thus after release from various sources, they stay in environment for a very long time. The fat containing foods like meat, milk, dairy products, fish and shell fish are prone to the contaminations of dioxins. The plants are also getting contaminated from dioxins. It enters the leafy vegetables from atmospheric deposition and contaminated water and then enters the food chain and become a part of the human food cycle.

The waste incinerators contributed to 66.7% of total dioxins release in the country. One of the most important reasons is open burning of municipal solid waste. Burning of rice straw in open field is the major source of dioxin and furan in India.

National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences continues to explore the detailed chemical pathway as dioxin functions. According to a recent research first step takes place when dioxin binds to intracellular proteins known as aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AhR). When this happens the AhR can alter the expression and function of certain genes. The resulting cellular imbalance leads to a disruption in normal cell function and ultimately adverse health effects.

The dioxin TCDD is a known cancer causing agent and other dioxin like compound are known to cause cancer in laboratory animals. Recently dioxin exposure is found to be

linked with type 2 diabetes, ischemic heart disease and chloracne like skin disease. It can also cause developmental problems in children infertility in adults result in miscarriages damage to immune system and interfere with hormones. Dioxin exposure can affect nearly every vertebrate species.

Pregnant women and their developing foetus may also be most sensitive. Due to Almost all humans are regularly exposed to low level of dioxin through inhalation, ingestion or skin contact, ingestion of food containing dioxins accounts for 90% exposure without knowing. Dioxins and Furans persist for a long period and have a tendency to bio accumulate which means they build up in Predators at the top of the food web. Most important thing about dioxins is that bioaccumulation of these pollutants occurs indirectly through contaminated food and water rather than breathing the contaminated air directly.

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In many countries dioxin content in food is well regulated. Dioxins are usually measured as *toxicity equivalent quantities* (TEQS) or parts per trillion (ppt) .Many countries have put regulations for the permissible intake of dioxin through food. Surprisingly India does not have any standard although annual release of dioxin and furan here is estimated to be 8656.55gTEQ. The waste incinerators contributed to 66.7% of total dioxins release in the country. One of the most important reasons is open burning of municipal solid waste. Burning of rice straw in open field is the major source of dioxin and furan in India.

Dioxins are hazardous to human health. Short term exposure may cause skin lesions, patchy darkening of the skin and altered liver, Thymus and Spleen functions. Immune system, endocrine system and reproductive systems are impaired. Chronic exposure may lead to several types of cancers. The dioxin TCDD is a known cancer causing agent and other dioxin like compound are known to cause cancer in laboratory animals. Recently dioxin exposure is found to be linked with type 2 diabetes, ischemic heart disease and chloracne like skin disease. It can also cause developmental problems in children infertility in adults result in miscarriages damage to immune system and interfere with hormones.

Pregnant women and their developing foetus may also be most sensitive. Due to high toxic potential of these background pollutants it is very necessary to reduce background exposure. In India condition is very difficult because here people yet to realize gravity of dioxin contaminations. Environmentalists agree that due to lack of any scientific studies no one knows the magnitudes of problems. Surprisingly there exists no data on dioxins levels in the country, while unsegregated plastic waste burning is the normal practice for disposal. According to Bharati chaturvedi (director of a NGO Chintan Environmental research and action group) rather than having large factories of dioxins in India, we have small factories spread all across the country where monitoring and enforcement becomes very difficult. The government offices themselves burn chlorinated waste and produce dioxins.

It is highly surprising that many medical colleges and institutes do not follow the prescribed norms. Burning of biomedical wastes and human anatomical parts in hospital incinerators was leading to toxic emissions which could cause cancers. While the problems of dioxins seem to be increasing by leaps and bounds in the country the government is tight lipped on the issue.

According to a report of National Institute of Environmental Health Science 2,3,7,8 (TCDD) tetra chlorodibenzo Para dioxin is a wide spread environmental contaminant, classified as known human carcinogen. Women who lived in most contaminated area (with TCDD) had been diagnosed with cancer. The dioxin present in the menstrual pads can cause ovarian cancer. Napkins are made to absorb wetness that's why aside from cotton they contain rayon and when rayon is bleached it releases dioxins. Unconsciously we are paying high price for being neat freaks. Such companies may argue that pads contain very low levels of dioxin .It employs the use of chlorine dioxide as the main bleaching agent so unless we are purchasing an organic product even those that say "dioxin free" on packaging or marketing materials may still contain traces of this harmful toxins. A woman might be using large number of napkins in their life time which can increase the risk for pelvic inflammatory diseases endometriosis and ovarian cancer.

Most surprisingly, most human beings have detectable levels of dioxins in their blood and tissues; if the person was never exposed to dioxin again the accumulation of dioxin up to

certain point would keep a constant level in his body for year's even decades.

Now question arises how to reduce dioxin exposure in food? It is very necessary to identify those areas with increased dioxin contaminations due to disposal and burning of contaminated materials. It is necessary to identify contaminated food and food ingredients especially dairy products and food containing high amount of fat deposits must be tested properly. Identification and control of critical food manufacturing processes (e.g. artificial drying by artificial heat) is necessary.

Conclusion

Dioxin release from industrial sources should be monitored regularly and best available technologies (BAT) for dioxin mitigation should be adopted. It is very necessary to check the contaminated food to enter the market. Sewage sludge used for agriculture purpose needs to be monitored. Live stock should be monitored to prevent contamination. The urgent need is that indiscriminate and uncontrolled burning of wastes should be immediately stopped and for it general public needs to be encouraged for source segregation, and in promotion of composting of household municipal wastes as far as possible. This will minimize waste burning. Educational Institutions, NGOs and Government agencies can play a crucial role in creating awareness amongst the masses otherwise we have created a toxin laden environment where future generation are left with nothing but polluted air, water and soil and empty handed regarding natural resources.

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